

**Studies on High Spin Cobalt(II) Complexes
of Some Bidentate and Tridentate
Schiff Bases**

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THE calculation of ligand field parameters viz., Racah's interelectronic parameter (B), cubic ligand field splitting parameter ($10 D_q$) and nephelauxetic effect (β), depends significantly on the method adopted for their calculations. König¹⁻³ has discussed the phenomenon of nephelauxetism and showed its importance in evaluating the covalency factors. The calculations of such parameters were reported earlier⁴⁻⁶ for six coordinated d^8 and d^9 ions i.e., V(II), Cr(III) and Ni(II). The present communication reports the coordination tendencies of some Schiff bases and the calculations of various ligand field parameters of the complexes of Co(II).

Experimental

Cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate used was AnalaR BDH and all other chemicals were of reagent grade. The ligands were prepared by the condensation of β -hydroxy- α -naphthaldehyde with 2-aminothiazole, orthonilic acid and aniline; furfural with *o*-toluidine and *o*-phenyldiamine with *p*-toluene sulphenyl chloride in absolute ethanol. These were purified by recrystallisation from absolute ethanol.

The estimations of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur were done at the micro analytical section of C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Cobalt content was estimated by complexometric titrations with EDTA⁷. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by Gouy method using mercury tetrathiocyanate cobaltate(II) as the calibrant ($\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ c.g.s. unit at 20°). Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants. Absorption spectra were recorded on a Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infrared spectrophotometer model 521 fitted with NaCl and KBr optices. The conductivity measurements were carried out on Philips conductivity bridge type LBR/B at room temperature.

(i) *2-(β -Hydroxynaphthalimine)thiazol Co(II) complex*: A solution of cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate (10 m mole) in ethanol (40 ml) was treated with the ligand (20 m mole) in the same solvent in the presence of a few drops of pyridine. A blackish green colour developed. The solution was refluxed

on a water-bath for 1 hr. On cooling and aerial concentration the dark green coloured crystals separated out. The compound was washed with water and finally with ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. Formula: $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{SO})_2]$. Anal. Found: C, 58.28; H, 3.24; N, 10.18; S, 10.87; Co, 10.44. Calcd.; C, 59.46; H, 3.18; N, 9.91; S, 11.32; Co, 10.44%. m.p., 280°.

(ii) *o-(β -Hydroxynaphthalimine)benzene sulphonic acid Co(II) complex*: This compound was prepared in a manner similar to that described above and an yellow compound was obtained. Formula: $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{NSO}_4)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. Anal. Found: C, 54.01; N, 3.93; S, 8.49; Co, 8.22. Calcd.; C, 55.96; H, 3.56; N, 3.84; S, 8.77; Cl, 8.09%. m.p. 270°.

(iii) *β -Hydroxynaphthalaniline Co(II) complex*: A solution of cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate (10 m mole) in ethanol (40 ml) was mixed with an ethanolic solution of the ligand (20 m mole) with constant stirring. On addition of sodium perchlorate to the solution a dark brown colour developed. This, on refluxing for 2 hr followed by cooling, gave the dark brown crystals. The brown crystals were washed with water and a little ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. Formula: $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{ON})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$. Anal. Found: C, 68.85; H, 4.87; N, 4.72; Co, 9.87. Calcd.; C, 69.50; H, 4.77; N, 4.77; Co, 10.05%. m.p. 280°.

(iv) *o-Toluylfurfuralimine Co(II) complex*: An ethanolic solution (50 ml) of cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate (10 m mole) was mixed with the ligand (20 m mole) in the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 1 hr and then concentrated to a small volume and cooled in ice bath. The greenish-black crystals obtained were filtered, washed with water followed by 95% ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. Formula: $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO})_2\text{Cl}_2]$. Anal. Found: C, 59.44; H, 4.31; N, 5.75; Cl, 14.65; Co, 11.57. Calcd.; C, 58.60; H, 4.40; N, 5.60; Cl, 14.20; Co, 11.80%. m.p. 285°.

(v) *o-(p-Toluylsulphonamido)aniline Co(II) complex*: A mixture containing cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate (10 m mole), ligand (30 m mole) and ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed on water bath for 2 hr and cooled in refrigerator. The wine coloured crystals were separated by filtration, washed with water and ethanol and dried *in vacuo*. Formula: $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{SO})_2]$. Anal. Found: C, 57.59; H, 4.86; N, 10.23; S, 10.96; Co, 7.07. Calcd.; C, 56.38; H, 4.97; N, 9.94; S, 10.36; Co, 6.98%. m.p. 282°.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are fairly stable at room temperature. The molar conductance values ($5-14 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$) in DMF at the concentration of 10^{-3} M show that these are non-electrolytes in DMF. The magnetic moment values lie in the range 4.60-4.90 B.M. which are well within the range expected for high spin octahedral geometry.

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The electronic spectra of the complexes consist of two main bands appearing at 9000-10500 cm⁻¹ and at 20500-22000 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to ⁴A_{2g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁) and ⁴A_{2g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν₂) transitions. The shoulders may be considered either as arising of the splitting of ν₃ in any components or because of the appearance of ν₃ transition².

The calculated values of the transitions ν₁, ν₂ and ν₃ may be obtained by the following equations^{2,3}:

$$\nu_1 = 1/2(10 Dq - 15 B) + 1/2[(10 Dq + 15 B)^2 - 12 B \cdot 10 Dq]^{1/2} \quad \dots \quad (i)$$

$$\nu_2 = 1/2(30 Dq - 15 B) + 1/2[(10 Dq + 15 B)^2 - 12 B \cdot 10 Dq]^{1/2} \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

$$\nu_3 = [(10 Dq + 15 B)^2 - 12 B \cdot 10 Dq]^{1/2} \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

and the values of Racah parameter and 10 Dq may then be calculated according to one of the following methods which differ by the bands on which fit is based:

$$B = (2\nu_1^2 - \nu_1\nu_2)/(12\nu_2 - 27\nu_1) \text{ and } 10 Dq = \nu_2 - \nu_1 \quad \dots \quad (a)$$

$$B = 1/30 - (2\nu_1 - \nu_2) \pm (\nu_1^2 + \nu_2^2 + \nu_1\nu_2)^{1/2} \text{ and } 10 Dq = 2\nu_1 - \nu_2 + 15 B \quad \dots \quad (b)$$

$$B = 1/510[7(\nu_2 - 2\nu_1) \pm 3\{81\nu_2^2 - 16\nu_1(\nu_2 - \nu_1)\}^{1/2}] \text{ and } 10 Dq = 1/3(2\nu_2 - \nu_1) + 5 B \quad \dots \quad (c)$$

$$B = (\nu_2 + \nu_3 - 3\nu_1)/15 \text{ and } 10 Dq = \nu_2 - \nu_1 \quad \dots \quad (d)$$

Out of the four methods applicable in the case of Co(II) complexes, the best fitting method is (b)

in which there is a good agreement between observed and the calculated values of transitions but in the cases of methods (c) and (d) there is a large percentage of deviation (δ%) Table 1. The method (a) is not applicable as the value of B was found to be negative which has no physical significance. The values of 10 Dq, B and β are presented in Table 1. The values of β of these complexes are between 0.5 and 1.0 and clearly indicate the partial covalent character of the bond concerned.

On comparison of ir spectra of the ligands and their corresponding Co(II) complexes, it is inferred that most of the frequencies are perturbed. In all the five [(i) to (v)] complexes, medium to strong intensity bands in the 1620-1600 cm⁻¹ region (attributed to -CH=N- stretching vibration) shift towards higher frequency in comparison to the free Schiff base, suggesting coordination of the Schiff base through the nitrogen of the azomethine group. The strong intensity bands in the 3520-3480 cm⁻¹ region in the ligands due to phenolic -OH group disappear in the spectra of complexes (i) to (iii), revealing the participation of the -OH group in chelation. The frequency 2600 cm⁻¹ (attributed to thiazol) shifts to 2550 cm⁻¹ in complex (i) indicating its involvement in chelation. A medium intensity band appeared at 1100 cm⁻¹ [assignable to ν(SO₃H)] was found to be absent in the complex (ii) suggesting coordination through sulphionate group. A strong band at 1250 cm⁻¹ (attributed to furfural group C-O-C) in free ligand was found to be shifted to 1160 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of complex (iv), indicating the participation

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND RELEVANT LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS

Method	Observed and calculated transition energies			10 Dq	B	β	δ%	LFSE
	⁴ A _{2g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)	⁴ T _{2g} (F)	⁴ T _{1g} (P)	cm ⁻¹	cm ⁻¹			kcal/mole
[Co(C ₁₄ H ₉ N ₃ SO ₂) ₂]								
Expt.	10000	19100	21200	—	—	—	—	—
(b)	fitted	21246	fitted	11247	829.8	0.85	11.23	19.22
(c)	8838	fitted	fitted	10160	898.8	0.91	11.62	17.41
(d)	8080	17180	fitted	9100	686.6	0.70	19.20	15.60
[Co(C ₁₇ H ₁₁ SNO ₄) ₂].H ₂ O								
Expt.	10500	19750	22000	—	—	—	—	—
(b)	fitted	22297	fitted	11796	853.0	0.87	12.81	20.22
(c)	9171	fitted	fitted	10422	917.0	0.94	12.84	17.86
(d)	8224	17474	fitted	9250	683.0	0.70	21.68	15.85
[Co(C ₁₇ H ₁₁ ON) ₂].2H ₂ O								
Expt.	9900	19000	21000	—	—	—	—	—
(b)	fitted	21032	fitted	11134	822.0	0.84	10.69	19.08
(c)	8894	fitted	fitted	10106	887.0	0.91	11.31	17.32
(d)	8080	17180	fitted	9100	686.6	0.70	18.38	15.00
[Co(C ₁₇ H ₁₁ NO) ₂ Cl ₂]								
Expt.	9150	18450	20500	—	—	—	—	—
(b)	fitted	19493	fitted	10698	836.3	0.86	5.34	17.70
(c)	8635	fitted	fitted	10175	870.0	0.80	5.96	16.80
(d)	8215	17515	fitted	9670	766.0	0.79	8.35	15.90
[Co(C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₂ SO ₂) ₂]								
Expt.	9000	18000	20500	—	—	—	—	—
(b)	fitted	19129	fitted	10192	846.0	0.87	5.77	17.50
(c)	8425	fitted	fitted	9595	883.0	0.91	6.82	16.50
(d)	7935	16935	fitted	9000	766.0	0.79	9.85	15.40

of the furfural group in chelation. It may be concluded therefore, that the ligand in complexes (i) and (ii) are tridentate while in the rest of the complexes the ligands are bidentate. Several new bands in the narrow range of 550-400 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(\text{Co}-\text{C})$, $\nu(\text{Co}-\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{Co}-\text{Cl})$ ⁹ further confirm the probable involvement of the above groups in chelation. In case of complex (iii) the presence of water molecules in coordination sphere was further checked by thermogravimetric analysis. Since no loss of weight of the complex was observed below 110°, we infer that the water is coordinated. In the case complex (ii), however, TGA indicated the presence of water as water of crystallisation.

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Alkaline Earth Metal Complexes : Mixed Ligand Complexes of Magnesium Tetrabromo Oxinate with Some Mono- and Bidentate Ligands

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As a part of our previous work¹ on mixed ligand complexes of magnesium oxinate, we are reporting here the synthesis of some mixed ligand complexes of magnesium tetrabromo oxinate with mono- and bi-dentate ligands.

Experimental

Our usual method of preparation was to take ethanolic solution of magnesium tetrabromo oxinate (corresponding magnesium oxinate was virtually insoluble) and add to it the ethanolic solution of the ligand in slight excess. The mixture was heated on hot plate and stirred for 8 to 10 hr after which it was allowed to cool in a refrigerator. On addition of ether to this cooled solution, the adducts separated out which were filtered, washed with acetone and dried at 90°.

Results and Discussion

The adducts of magnesium tetrabromo oxinate, which are generally yellow in colour, are stable when stored under dry conditions but slowly absorb moisture when exposed to air. These complexes are soluble in polar solvents but insoluble in non-polar solvents. The adducts have higher melting points than the stoichiometric mixture of their ingredients; the transition or decomposition temperature of the complexes are much higher than that of the ligands, showing their greater stability. The colour, decomposition or transition temperatures and analytical values of the adducts are given in Table I.

On comparison of the decomposition/transition temperatures of these complexes with those of the complexes formed by anhydrous magnesium oxinate¹, having the common ligands for both, it has been observed that these are more stable and have higher transition/decomposition temperatures. This difference in stability may be accounted for by assuming that presence of bromine in positions 5 and 7 in magnesium tetrabromo oxinate increases the donor property of this ligand. All these complexes are highly soluble in ethanol, whereas the corresponding mixed ligand magnesium oxinate complexes¹ are all insoluble.

An examination of the infrared spectra of the compound formed with water molecules and magnesium tetrabromo oxinate, shows an extra peak at 862 cm^{-1} , which may be of coordinated water². The infrared spectra of pyridine adducts only show some extra peaks due to the presence of pyridine molecule. Of the two N-H stretching vibrations of ethylenediamine, the 3380 cm^{-1} peak remains unaffected, but the 3316 cm^{-1} peak appears at 3250 cm^{-1} with reduced intensity in the complex. In *o*-phenylenediamine complex, a lower shift of 40 cm^{-1} in the 3316 cm^{-1} peak has been observed.

The spectra of the adducts formed with catechol and ethyleneglycol show a number of unexpected features: (a) one of the O-H stretching frequency of catechol is missing and the second O-H stretching frequency is shifted by about 200 cm^{-1} showing association, (b) a new broad band of medium intensity with submaxima at 2750 cm^{-1} and another at 2600 cm^{-1} are seen in the complex, which are absent in the ingredients. These peaks have been assigned to N...H...O bonding in the complex, (c) another broad band at 1950-1850 cm^{-1} is also seen in the complexes, which is assigned to strong hydrogen bonding O...H...O.

The spectra of the complexes formed with anthranilic acid, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, *o*-nitrophenol, salicylaldehyde show strong hydrogen bond bands between 2700-2650 and/or 1900-1800 cm^{-1} which are missing in the components. In 1-nitroso-2-naphthol complex, the N=O band at 1640 cm^{-1} in the ligand appears at 1620 cm^{-1} in the complex, while for *o*-nitrophenol adduct, the N=O band appears at 1605 cm^{-1} in the complex.